

Vibrations of Euler-Bernoulli Beam with Non-uniform Cross-Sections

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Abstract

The analysis of vibrations in Euler-Bernoulli beams with non-uniform cross-sections is related to the dynamic behavior of beams that do not have a constant cross-sectional area along their length. The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory is commonly used for such analyses, assuming that the beam experiences small deformations and rotations. The mathematical model is formulated for the Euler-Bernoulli beam with non-uniform cross-sections. For governing the beam's behavior, considering the effects of bending and shear, the differential equations are introduced. Material and geometric properties represent variations in properties such as Young's modulus, density, and cross-sectional area. The mode shapes and natural frequencies of the non-uniform Euler-Bernoulli beam are obtained by solving the eigenvalue problem. The transient or steady-state response are analyzed via appropriate mathematical techniques. The study aims to ensure that the modeling assumptions and boundary conditions accurately represent the physical system.

Keywords: Euler-Bernoulli beam, non-uniform beam, linear vibrations

Introduction

In structural engineering, understanding the behavior of beams with non-uniform cross-sections is vital for the design and safety of buildings and infrastructure. The cross-sectional shape and size of a beam significantly affects its mechanical properties such as strength, stiffness and stability.

Analysis of beams with different cross-sectional areas provides information on how these shapes affect the distribution of internal forces and moments. The stress distribution within a beam depends directly on the cross-section geometry, which determines the beam's moment of inertia and therefore its ability to resist bending and shear forces. This is essential for the analysis and design of building elements [1].

A comprehensive summary of the methods used to evaluate beams with various cross-sectional shapes and the importance of accurately determining the moment of inertia for different geometries is presented by Hibbeler [2]. Demir et al. [3] further develop the methods in the analysis of such beams by presenting a new approach to the dynamic analysis of structural elements modeled with singular functions. Şimşek et al. [4] examined the dynamic behavior of functionally graded axial beams under moving harmonic load, contributing to understanding the performance of such beams under dynamic loads. Çalım [5] investigated the dynamic behavior of the free and forced vibrations of non-uniform composite beams under various boundary conditions.

In general, the examination of beams of non-uniform cross-sections is a complex but fundamental aspect of structural engineering. Understanding how different geometries affect the mechanical properties of beams allows engineers to design more effective and hardness structures. In this study, instead of a single mathematical model with singularity functions for the analysis of a beam with different cross-sections, the beam is divided into two regions and a more solvable model is presented for each span. Thus, it allows us to have information about the displacement, natural frequency and critical axial load of the system.

Equation of Motion

The equation of motion of an axially loaded Euler Bernoulli beam is presented as [1]

$$(E I \tilde{w}''')'' + (P \tilde{w}')' + \rho A \tilde{w} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where E represents the modulus of elasticity, I indicates the moment of inertia (strength, that is, rigidity), P represents the axial load (hardness up to a certain value). A is defined as cross-sectional area, ρ is density of beam material, $w(x, t)$ represents the displacement. $()'$ shows the derivative with respect to spatial (\tilde{x}) and $(\dot{\ })$ represents the derivative with respect to time (\tilde{t}).

Figure 1. An Euler-Bernoulli beam with non-uniform cross-sections

The problem considered is a beam with non-uniform cross sections. It is taken into account assuming that the beam is subject to small deformations and rotations. The considered problem has variable coefficients and the analytical solution of this type of equation is difficult. For this reason, semi-analytical or approximate solutions are needed. In order to overcome these difficulties, the beam can be divided into two regions and fourth order linear partial differential equation with constant coefficients can be written for each region in the form of

$$E_1 I_1 \tilde{w}_1^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_1'' + \rho_1 A_1 \tilde{w}_1 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$E_2 I_2 \tilde{w}_2^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_2'' + \rho_2 A_2 \tilde{w}_2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

subject to the transition and the boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{w}_1(0, \tilde{t}) = 0 & & \tilde{w}_1(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{w}_2(x_1, \tilde{t}) & & \tilde{w}_1(1, \tilde{t}) = 0 \\ \tilde{w}_1''(0, \tilde{t}) = 0 & & \tilde{w}_1'(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{w}_2'(x_1, \tilde{t}) & & \tilde{w}_2''(1, \tilde{t}) = 0 \\ & & \tilde{w}_1''(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \alpha_{I_2} \tilde{w}_2''(x_1, \tilde{t}) & & \\ & & \tilde{w}_1'''(x_1, \tilde{t}) + P \tilde{w}_1'(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \alpha_{I_2} \tilde{w}_2'''(x_1, \tilde{t}) + P \tilde{w}_2'(x_1, \tilde{t}) & & \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For evading shape and material dependency, non-dimensionalization of Eqs. (2)-(3) yields

$$w_1^{iv} + P w_1'' + \tilde{w}_1 = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_{I_2} w_2^{iv} + P w_2'' + \alpha_{A_2} \tilde{w}_2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

where new dimensionless terms are

$$\begin{aligned} w = \frac{\tilde{w}_1 L}{r^2}, \quad t = \frac{\tilde{t}}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E_1 I_1}{\rho_1 A_1}}, \quad x = \frac{\tilde{x}}{L}, \quad r = \sqrt{\frac{I_1}{A_1}}, \quad P = \tilde{P} \frac{E_1 I_1}{L^2} \\ \alpha_{I_2} = \frac{I_2}{I_1} \quad \alpha_{A_2} = \frac{A_2}{A_1} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Solution Method

Assuming that the variation with time is harmonic, the solution for the equation in first region can be written as follows

$$w_1(x, t) = X_1(x) e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (8)$$

If the solution (8) is substituted into (5), the fourth order ordinary differential equation with constant coefficient is obtained as

$$X_1^{iv}(x) + P X_1''(x) - \omega_n^2 X_1(x) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Similarly, we can suggest a solution as follows for second region

$$w_2(x, t) = X_2(x) e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (10)$$

Substituting the solution (10) into Eq. (6), one obtains

$$\alpha_{I_2} X_2^{iv}(x) + P X_2''(x) - \alpha_{A_2} \omega_n^2 X_2(x) = 0 \quad (11)$$

If the boundary and transition conditions are rearranged, then

$$\begin{aligned} X_1(0) &= 0 & X_1(x_1) &= X_2(x_1) & X_2(1) &= 0 \\ X_1''(0) &= 0 & X_1'(x_1) &= X_2'(x_1) & X_2''(1) &= 0 \\ & & X_1(x_1) &= \alpha_{I_2} X_2''(x_1) & & \\ & & X_1'''(x_1) + P X_1'(x_1) &= \alpha_{I_2} X_2'''(x_1) + P X_2'(x_1) & & \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

For first region, the solution of equation (9) is

$$X_1(x) = c_1 e^{r_1 x} + c_2 e^{r_2 x} + c_3 e^{r_3 x} + c_4 e^{r_4 x} \quad (13)$$

where the roots of the characteristic equation are

$$r_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\sqrt{P^2 + 4\omega_n^2} - 2P}}{2} \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the solution of equation (11) for second region is

$$X_2(x) = a_1 e^{s_1 x} + a_2 e^{s_2 x} + a_3 e^{s_3 x} + a_4 e^{s_4 x} \quad (15)$$

where the roots of the characteristic equation are

$$s_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\alpha_{I_2}(-P + \sqrt{4\alpha_{I_2}\alpha_{A_2}\omega_n^2 + P^2})}}{2\alpha_{I_2}} \quad (16)$$

Numerical Results

In this section, some beam models with non-uniform cross-sections will be introduced.

Figure 2. The beam with different height and same width

Table 1. The variations of natural freq., ω_n for different height and same width ($\alpha_{I_2} = \frac{8}{27}$ $\alpha_{A_2} = \frac{2}{3}$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
$P = 0$	27.10644560	31.29316407	33.32118901	35.37776136
$P = 3$	23.74771694	28.56873506	30.97194851	33.38737288

Table 2. The variation of critical value of P for $\omega_n=0$ ($\alpha_{I_2} = \frac{8}{27}$ $\alpha_{A_2} = \frac{2}{3}$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
P	18.73293725	14.67435053	11.47159697	10.10322574

In Figure 1, it is observed that as the cross-sectional area increased, the stiffness increased.

Figure 3. The beam with different width and same height

In Figure 2, as the transition region value increases due to the size of the second section, the stiffness and critical axial load value, P decreases.

Table 3. The variations of natural freqs., ω_n for different width and same height ($\alpha_{I_2} = 2, \alpha_{A_2} = 2$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
$P = 0$	38.77338065	39.70367949	39.70367949	38.77338065
$P = 4$	37.61482133	38.25077698	38.15208940	36.91069791

Table 4. The variation of critical value of P for $\omega_n=0$ ($\alpha_{I_2} = 2, \alpha_{A_2} = 2$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
P	2.272740809	2.755902419	4.191738558	7.990782603

Figure 4. The beam with different width and height

In Figure 4, the stiffness increases, as the length of the section of first region increases in this model where both heights and widths are different. Likewise, the axial load value P also increases. This case is valid for natural frequency.

Table 5. The variations of natural frequencies, ω_n for different width and height ($\alpha_{I_2} = \frac{2}{9}, \alpha_{A_2} = \frac{1}{2}$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
$P = 0$	26.66737974	31.06062372	33.88573241	34.57841283
$P = 2$	23.78578752	28.77866959	32.0606618450	33.10524221
$P = 6$	22.20108624	27.55717483	31.11461076	32.33809718

Table 6. The variation of critical value of P ($\omega_n=0$)

x_1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8
P	2.272740809	2.755902419	4.191738558	7.990782603

Conclusion

The critical load value is the smallest value, P that forces the structure to buckle. When this load exceeds this value, the structure loses its stability. Smaller displacements are expected at larger natural frequency values. Considering the numerical results, it is expected that the stiffness of the structural element increases as the section length increases in the first beam model. It is seen that as the stiffness increases, the critical axial load and natural frequency also increase. In the beam model with different width and same height, due to the larger section of the second region, as the value, x_1 increases, the stiffness decreases and the axial load decreases. If these two models are compared, while the moment of inertia and the width of the section change linearly, its effect on stiffness will be less than the height. In the final model, where both heights and widths are different, the size of the section of first region is larger, and as the value, x_1 increases, the rigidity and critical axial load values also increase

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